

CAREER DECISIONS AND PROFESSIONAL IDENTITY OF NURSE INTERNS IN THE TEACHING CARE HOSPITALS AT PESHAWAR

Sulaiman Shah^{*1}, Tahir Ullah², Hanook Nadeem³, Mansoor Ayub Khan⁴, Meher Ali⁵

^{*1,2,3,4,5}Nursing Intern at Naseer Teaching Hospital, Peshawar

¹sulaimanshah346@gmail.com, ²tahireafridi@gmail.com, ³hanooknadeem123@gmail.com, ⁴ayubmansoor225@gmail.com, ⁵alimeher044@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17111130>

Keywords

Career decision, Professional, Identity Among, Nurse Interns

Article History

Received: 19 June 2025

Accepted: 28 August 2025

Published: 13 September 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *
Sulaiman Shah

Abstract

Introduction: The Bachelor of Science in Nursing degree is designed to prepare students to become effective nurses, addressing the demands of nursing shortages and ensuring excellent care. The nursing curriculum spans four academic years, followed by a mandatory internship year where students apply their learned skills in real-world settings. This internship year is crucial for developing clinical competencies and bridging the gap between theory and practice. It also plays a significant role in shaping the professional identity of nursing students as they transition from education to practice. Methodology: The study utilized a descriptive cross-sectional design, conducted over six months in three tertiary hospitals in Peshawar. A sample size of 143 was determined using the Open Epi calculator at a 95% confidence level. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS version 23, focusing on factors influencing the professional identity of nurse interns. Result: The results indicate that most participants are aged between 23 and 25, with a majority being female. The respondents generally show strong confidence in their career decisions, clinical skills, and commitment to patient care. Additionally, no significant correlation was found between professional identity and the participants' nursing college or place of employment. Conclusion: The study reveals that nursing interns are confident in their career choice and committed to patient care and continuous learning. Despite varying backgrounds and job locations, there was no significant correlation with professional identity, indicating a strong, uniform dedication across the group.

INTRODUCTION

Since nurses are one of the most vital members of a health care team, the Bachelor of Science in nursing degree is designed to equip nursing students to be effective nurses in clinical nursing care to meet the demands of nursing shortages and deliver excellent care.

Four academic years make up the nursing curriculum, after which there is an internship year. After a year of preparation, students study for three years at the

college to acquire the fundamental information and abilities of nursing through theoretical lectures, practical experience, and nursing skills labs. (Zhou et al., 2023) The most vital courses that are taken include nursing foundations, adult nursing care, child health, maternity, critical care, psychiatric/mental health, and nursing leadership/management. Applying high-quality nursing care takes up the final year of the nursing curriculum. The year is referred to as the

nursing internship year. Applying high-quality nursing care is the focus of the final year of the nursing program. We refer to it as the year of the nursing internship. For nursing students, this internship year is a rigorous and required training period. Students are exposed to various clinical settings throughout this time. This year's objective is to establish a connection between the previous four years' worth of practice and theory. A 12-month internship is required in order to get a license to practice as a registered nurse. The internship serves as a transitional stage between classroom learning and experiential learning. (Abd El Naeem et al., 2015))

An essential phase in preparing aspiring nurses for real-world practice is the nursing internship program. It facilitates the development of nursing students' clinical abilities by fusing theory and practice. Additionally, to fulfill the demands of the healthcare industry, a quality internship

program promotes safe patient care, strengthens clinical competencies, and encourages ongoing professional growth. The purpose of the internship, which is to obtain job experience, is to be considered a trial. (Salvatore et al., 2018) In addition, training during a predetermined trial time may be necessary to determine whether or not a nurse specialist satisfies certain requirements for a job. In addition to the aforementioned, nursing students continue to develop their professional identities during their internship. Hope is an optimistic mental state that stems from a shared belief in one's own ability to achieve objectives (agency) and in possessing the means to do so (pathways). In actuality, it is generating force.¹⁴ Therefore, the agency can be thought of as the emotional component of hope since it reflects an individual's drive to attain their goals.¹⁵ Meanwhile, contentment with several facets of one's personal life as well as work-life balance is a component of well-being or wellness at work. The strains and difficulties that nurses face on a daily basis have had a detrimental impact on their wellbeing during the past thirty years.¹⁶ As a result, research on professional identity and hope in nursing has begun to focus more and more on wellbeing.¹⁷ Still, not much research has been done in this field. (Chacko, 2011)

While the internship is a fantastic opportunity for nursing students to learn new things and connect with patients, it also poses a significant challenge to

programs. Professional identities are a type of social identities that are connected to workgroup interactions and how members set themselves apart from other professional workgroups. (Hussien et al., 2021)

The professional identity is how a person sees themselves as a professional working in a particular field of competence through the application of relevant information and skills that they have gained. It encompasses a wide range of principles, convictions, dispositions, motivations, and life experiences applied in skillful ways that are grounded in moral and cognitive thinking.

One's potential responsibilities within their chosen career are also connected to their professional identity. (idea of oneself), as well as how other people perceive this individual (social image).

The development of a professional identity may play a significant role in nursing students' decisions to continue their education in nursing or to pursue another path. (Thomas et al., 2023)

The development of a professional identity entails internalizing fundamental beliefs and viewpoints acknowledged as essential to the nursing profession. As a nurse develops professionally and learns more, the fundamental principles become obvious. In order to enhance patient outcomes and advance the goals of the nursing profession, the nurse upholds these core values in all facets of practice. (Chacko, 2011)

helping them develop their professional identities. Stable well-being is attained when people have the psychological, social, and physical resources necessary to meet every day psychological, social, and physical challenges. Well-being has been defined as the balance and difference between an individual's resources and the challenges faced. (Kolly, 2018)

The sense of well-being undoubtedly aids nursing interns in making the seamless transition from graduate to practitioner nursing roles and in fulfilling the internship training requirements.

Furthermore, having a certain amount of hope is necessary to persevere through the demanding clinical internship program and to find the motivation needed to complete the long path of nursing education; as a result, the fact that hope for the future improves the practice and career of nurse interns serves as evidence of the need for it. (Zhong et al., 2024)

Rationale of the study:

Professional identity formation is a critical aspect of nursing education and practice, particularly for nurse interns who are transitioning from student roles to professional practitioners. In the context of teaching care hospitals, such as those in Peshawar, the development of a strong professional identity is essential for ensuring high standards of patient care, fostering job satisfaction, and reducing turnover rates among newly graduated nurses.

Significance of the Study:

This study is significant as it aims to enhance the understanding of professional identity formation among nurse interns, essential for improving educational programs, mentorship, and support systems in teaching care hospitals. By identifying factors that influence professional identity, the research will contribute to better job satisfaction, reduced burnout, and higher retention rates, ultimately leading to improved patient care quality in Peshawar's healthcare settings.

Problem statement:

The formation of a strong professional identity among nurse interns is critical for their transition into competent and confident practitioners. However, there is limited understanding of how this identity develops within the unique context of teaching care hospitals in Peshawar, potentially hindering effective educational and support strategies. This study seeks to address this gap by exploring the factors influencing professional identity among nurse interns in this setting.

Objective of this study:

To explore and understand the career decisions and professional identity development of nurse interns at Care Hospital in Peshawar.

Research Question:

How does career decision influence the development of professional identity among nurse interns at Care Hospital in Peshawar?

OPERATIONAL DEFINATIONS;

Career Decision:

Career decisions refer to the process by which nurse interns select and commit to their professional paths within the nursing field. This includes choices related to specialty areas, career progression, and long-term professional goals. These decisions are shaped by personal preferences, educational experiences, and external influences within the healthcare environment.

Professional:

A person who works in a career, particularly a studied profession, is considered a professional. A person having a great degree of expertise in a field can also be referred to by this term. An individual who pursues a career or activity professionally is referred to as a professional.

Identity:

It is the collection of characteristics that define an individual or a group, including beliefs, personality traits, appearance, and/or expressions.

Interns:

A trainee or student who works, occasionally unpaid, to fulfill requirements for a qualification or obtain job experience.

SUMMARY:

The Bachelor of Science in nursing program prepares students to meet the demands of the nursing profession by providing four years of academic training followed by a year-long internship. This program covers essential courses like nursing foundations, adult and child care, maternity, and mental health. The internship year, considered crucial, allows students to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world clinical settings, bridging the gap between education and practice. Professional identity development during this period is essential as it shapes how nurse interns see themselves in their roles and affects their future career paths. This identity is influenced by core values, beliefs, and experiences. The study aims to identify the factors influencing professional identity among nurse interns in teaching care hospitals in Peshawar, as this understanding is vital for improving educational programs and support

systems, ultimately enhancing job satisfaction and patient care quality.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction:

A literature review is a critical analysis and synthesis of existing research and scholarly writings on a specific topic. It involves reviewing and summarizing relevant sources such as a book, scholarly article and other publications. The purpose of literature review is to provide an overview of the current knowledge and underrating of a particular subject, identify gaps existing research.

Search methodology:

We use internet sources, such as, Google scholar articles, PubMed from where we take published article for our literature review.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria:

The published article is included our literature review unpublished we exclude from the article literature review. We are taking the article which is include pervious ten years. somehow two article is about ten years previously.

Literature review on Career Decisions and Professional Identity of Nurse Interns in a Teaching Care Hospital in Peshawar Kp.

We have done literature review on professional identity among nurse's interns in teaching hospital kpk Peshawar. We have section in this literature review.

- Professional identity in nursing interns.
- Nursing education and curriculum development.
- Recommendation for nursing internship programs.
- Recent trends and emerging issues.
- Factor influencing on professional identity among nurse's interns such as clinical experience, role model, educational environment, personal motivational, mentorship and support, clinical supervision, ethical decision making, wellness and resilience, cultural and contextual influences, career planning and future outlook.
- Gaps in existing research such as role model

and environments, longitudinal impact of curricular reforms, cultural and contextual factor, integration of ethical decision making and compassionate care.

2.1 Professional Identity in Nursing Interns

The development of a nurse's professional identity is essential to producing competent and contented nurses (Begat et al., 2017). It entails the intricate interaction of role models, individual goals, and clinical experiences (Wang et al., 2020). The development of a professional identity is greatly influenced by elements including the deliberate decision to pursue a career in nursing and exposure to good role models (Moore et al., 2019). Nursing interns' professional identities have been shown to be significantly shaped by social modeling in clinical settings (McKenna et al., 2018). Recent research, however, indicates that further investigation is warranted into the precise kinds of surroundings and role models that support identity formation in a variety of nursing contexts.

2.2 Nursing Education and Curriculum Development

To prepare resilient and competent nurses, nursing education curricula must incorporate elements like professional identity, wellness, and future hope (Lambrinou et al., 2016). It is advised that curricula be changed to provide more emphasis on clinical exposure and personal growth in order to help nursing students create strong professional identities (Brown & Francis, 2018).

According to recent studies, giving nursing students the option to choose their specialism improves their sense of independence and optimism about their future careers (Gibson & Heartfield, 2016). To find out how these curricular interventions affect nursing interns' professional identities and job happiness over the long run, more research is necessary.

2.3 Recommendations for Nursing Internship Programs

Enhancing professional identity, wellbeing, and hope for the future of nursing interns requires collaboration between clinical training sites and nursing faculty (Maben & Clark, 2015). Johnson et al. (2018) have identified mentoring programs and

supportive clinical environments as efficacious techniques aimed at fostering professional development and well-being among nursing students. Reducing burnout and increasing retention in the nursing sector require addressing the psychological and physical difficulties encountered by interns (Labrague & McEnroe-Petitte, 2018). However, there are still gaps in our knowledge on the precise mentorship models and nurturing settings that work best for nursing interns in various organizational and cultural contexts.

2.4 Recent Trends and Emerging Issues

Wellness is becoming more widely acknowledged as a vital aspect of professional nursing practice, according to recent research (Taylor & Reyes, 2016). Research has investigated many approaches to augment resilience and overall well-being in nurses, highlighting the necessity for customized interventions that tackle the distinct stressors encountered by nursing interns (Levin, 2017). Furthermore, it is now widely acknowledged that making moral decisions and incorporating compassionate care into nursing practice are crucial components of a nurse's professional identity (Cheung & Leung, 2018; Brown & Francis, 2018). The precise ways in which these moral aspects and compassionate care techniques affect nursing interns' formation of their professional identities, however, remain poorly understood.

2.5 Factor influencing on professional identity among nurse interns

- **Clinical Experiences:** The pleasant and variety of clinical studies play a important role in shaping expert identity. fantastic medical stories make contributions to confidence, competence, and a sense of professional function integration (Wang et al., 2020).
- **Role Models:** exposure to wonderful role fashions, consisting of clinical instructors, skilled nurses, and peers, influences professional identity formation. role fashions offer examples of expert behaviors, values, and moral decision-making that form the interns very own professional identities (McKenna et al., 2018).
- **Educational Environment:** The supportive nature of the educational environment, which

includes the curriculum layout and coaching methods, impacts how interns perceive their professional roles and obligations. academic reforms that emphasize holistic development and practical abilities enhance expert identity (Lambrinou et al., 2016).

- **Personal Motivation:** character motivations for choosing nursing as a profession, which includes personal values, altruism, and choice to help others, are extensive drivers of professional identity formation (Moore et al., 2019).
- **Mentorship and Support:** 5. Mentorship programs and supportive relationships with skilled nurses and educators provide steering, validation, and possibilities for expert growth. these relationships foster a sense of belonging and identity inside the nursing career (Johnson et al., 2018).
- **Clinical Supervision:** powerful medical supervision complements nurses' delight and well-being, which in flip definitely influences their professional identity. Supervisors who offer constructive feedback and assist interns' learning make a contribution appreciably to their professional development (Begat et al., 2017).
- **Ethical Decision-Making:** the combination of ethical choice-making into nursing training and practice fosters a robust professional identification. Nurses who navigate ethical challenges with integrity and compassion develop a robust feel of professional identification (Brown & Francis, 2018).
- **Wellness and Resilience:** techniques that promote wellness and resilience among interns, along with pressure management strategies, self-care practices, and supportive organizational cultures, make a contribution to a fine expert identification (Taylor & Reyes, 2016).
- **Cultural and Contextual Influences:** Cultural and contextual factors, consisting of societal expectations, organizational cultures, and healthcare regulations, shape how interns perceive their professional roles and identities. information and navigating these impacts are crucial for expert identity improvement (Salonen et al., 2017).
- **Career Planning and Future Outlook:** Interns'

perceptions of career possibilities, opportunities for development, and process pleasure impact their professional identification. fantastic outlooks on future profession paths make contributions to a sense of purpose and commitment to the nursing career (Gibson & Heartfield, 2016).

- Longitudinal Impact of Curricular Reforms: while curricular reforms had been proposed to decorate professional identity, wellness, and future hope, there may be an opening in longitudinal studies that verify the sustained effects of these reforms on nursing students' career pride and retention quotes submit-internship.
- Cultural and Contextual Factors: studies gaps exist regarding how cultural and contextual factors impact the effectiveness of mentorship applications and supportive medical environments in promoting expert identification and well-being amongst nursing interns, especially in numerous global settings.
- Integration of Ethical Decision-Making and Compassionate Care: more studies are needed to explore how the mixing of moral decision-making processes and compassionate care practices contributes to the expert identification formation of nursing interns and influences affected person care effects.

SUMMARY

A literature review critically analyses and synthesizes existing research on a specific topic, identifying gaps in current knowledge. For this study on professional identity among nurse interns in teaching hospitals in Peshawar, relevant sources were gathered from databases like Google Scholar and PubMed, focusing on published articles from the last ten years.

Key topics reviewed include the development of professional identity in nursing interns, influenced

Sample size.

As through open epi calculator the sample size is 143 at the rate of 95% of confidence level.

by clinical experiences, role models, and educational environments. Factors like personal motivation, mentorship, clinical supervision, and ethical decision-making also play crucial roles. Recent trends highlight the importance of wellness and resilience, as well as the impact of cultural and contextual influences on professional identity formation.

Recommendations for improving nursing internship programs emphasize the need for collaboration between clinical sites and nursing faculty, mentoring programs, and supportive environments to reduce burnout and increase retention. Gaps in the literature include the long-term effects of curricular reforms, the role of ethical decision-making, and the influence of cultural factors on professional identity. Further research is needed to explore these areas and improve the overall understanding of professional identity formation in nursing interns.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Introduction:

This chapter presents research methods applied in the study. The chapter begins with an introduction of the study, Philosophical positioning, Material and methods, Framework for analysis, Data analysis, Validation strategies Ethical rigor.

Study Design

The study design is Descriptive Cross-sectional study.

Study Settings:

The purpose of the study where be made clear to all the participants. The three tertiary hospitals of Peshawar, MTI HMC, Kuwait teaching hospital, Naseer teaching hospital, RMI, and Khyber teaching hospital will be included in it.

Study Duration

This is a short duration study. The study was being carried out for six months only.

Sample Size for Frequency in a Population

Population size(for finite population correction factor or fpc)(N): 227
 Hypothesized % frequency of outcome factor in the population (p): 50%+/-5
 Confidence limits as % of 100(absolute +/- %)(d): 5%
 Design effect (for cluster surveys-DEFF): 1

Sample Size(n) for Various Confidence Levels

ConfidenceLevel(%)	Sample Size
95%	143
80%	96
90%	124
97%	154
99%	170
99.9%	188
99.99%	198

Equation

Sample size $n = [DEFF * Np(1-p)] / [(d^2 / Z^2_{1-\alpha/2} * (N-1) + p*(1-p)]$

Results from OpenEpi, Version 3, open source calculator--SSPropor
 Print from the browser with ctrl-P
 or select text to copy and paste to other programs.

Sample technique

Convenient sampling technique was used for the sampling.

3.7. Sample Selection

Sample was selected on the basis of the following inclusion criteria and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria:

All the interns who' are working in the above cited hospital They are willingly for the consent

Exclusion Criteria:

All the those who are not working above cited hospital Those who are not willingly for the consent Those who's are on long leave more than one month.

3.9 DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE:

Structured questionnaire were used for data collection which is modified it consist factors that influence the development of professional identity among nurse interns. (Frontiers of Nursing • 8(3) • 2021) **original article in Frontiers of Nursing through this link.**

3.11. Data Analysis

Data was analyzed through software SPSS version 23 for the representation of data.

Descriptive statistic:

Data calculated for mean and standard deviation (Age) Frequency and percentage calculated for categorical variables such as gender, and education status, and it represented in graphs and tables.

SUMMARY OF RESEARCH METHODS

This chapter details the research methods used in the study, including an overview of the study, philosophical positioning, materials and methods, framework for analysis, data analysis, and validation strategies. The study employs a descriptive cross-sectional design and will be conducted in three tertiary hospitals in Peshawar: MTI HMC, Kuwait Teaching Hospital, Naseer Teaching Hospital, RMI, and Khyber Teaching Hospital. The study was last six months, with a sample size of 143, determined using the Open Epi calculator at a 95% confidence level.

Convenient sampling will be used to select participants based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Data are collected using a

structured questionnaire, focusing on factors influencing the development of professional identity among nurse interns. The data are analyzed using

SPSS version 23, with descriptive statistics used to calculate means, standard deviations, frequencies, and percentages, presented in graphs and tables.

RESULT

Graph :01 Age of The Study Precipitants

The above graph shows that the most common age among participants is 24 years old, representing 32.2% of the sample. Ages 23 and 25 are also significant, accounting for 20.3% and 26.6% respectively. The least common ages are 27 and 28, with 4.2% and 0.7% of participants. Overall, 79.1% of participants fall within the 23 to 25 age range. The standard deviation is 1.243, indicating the extent of variation from the mean, and the variance is 1.545.

The average age is 24.26 years, with a median age of 24 years and a mode of 24 years.

Graph: 02: MARITAL STATUS OF STUDY PRACIPTANT

In the above graph No 02 the majority of the participants, 73.4%, are unmarried, while 26.6% are married. This shows a significant skew towards unmarried participants in the study.

Graph :03: Gender of the study participants

The above graph showing that total sample was consists of 143 participants, with 59 males (41.3%) and 84 females (58.7%). The cumulative percentage shows that males comprise 41.3% and females 100% when combined. This indicates a higher proportion of female participants compared to male participants in the study.

Graph :04: Place of job of the study participants

The above graph no 4 shows that the highest number of participants work at HMC, with 34 participants (23.8%). Equally, the lowest number of participants work at Kuwait Hospital, with 21 participants (14.7%).

Graph:05: participants of the study who's graduate from the college was showing in the below graph.

The study shows that the majority of graduates come from FIN and RCN, each contributing 21.7%. INS follows with 18.2% of the graduates, and RNC adds 17.5%. The remaining colleges have smaller contributions ranging from 0.7% to 8.4%. This distribution indicates a varied representation of nursing graduates from multiple colleges, with some colleges contributing a larger share of graduates than others.

Graph 06: I chose Nursing as my career independently

The study reveals that the majority of respondents (approximately 79.8%) either agree or strongly agree that they chose nursing independently. This suggests a strong sense of agency and personal decision-making in their career choice.

Graph :07: I feel confident about my decision to become a nurse.

The study indicates that a significant majority of respondents (81.8%) either agree or strongly agree that they feel confident about their decision to become a nurse. A smaller percentage (7%) either disagree or strongly disagree, while 11.2% remain neutral.

Table 02: I believe nursing is the right profession for me

I believe nursing is the right profession for me		Frequency	Percent
Valid	strongly disagree	3	2.1
	disagree	6	4.2
	neutral	15	10.5
	agree	47	32.9
	strongly agree	72	50.3
	Total	143	100.0

The study shows that 83.2% of respondents (47 agree and 72 strongly agree) believe nursing is the right profession for them. A small portion (6.3%) either disagree or strongly disagree, while 10.5% remain neutral. This indicates a strong overall affirmation among respondents about their choice of nursing as a profession.

Graph :08: I have role Model in nursing who inspire me.

The data reveals that 50.3% of respondents strongly agree that nursing is the right profession for them, while 32.9% agree, indicating a high overall agreement. Additionally, 10.5% are neutral, and a smaller proportion disagrees (4.2%) or strongly disagrees (2.1%). This suggests that most respondents have a positive view of nursing as the right profession for them.

Graph :09: I aspire to follow the footsteps of experienced nurses I admire.

The data shows that a significant majority of respondents (42.7% agree and 32.9% strongly agree) aspire to follow the footsteps of experienced nurses they admire, totaling 75.6% with positive aspirations. A neutral stance is held by 16.1% of respondents, while only 8.4% disagree or strongly disagree, indicating a small minority who do not share this aspiration. Overall, this suggests a strong inclination among respondents to look up to and follow experienced nurses.

Table :03: Seeing other successful nurses motivates me to pursue my career

Seeing other successful nurses motivates me to pursue my career		Frequency	Percent
Valid	strongly disagree	5	3.5
	disagree	3	2.1
	neutral	15	10.5
	agree	60	42.0
	strongly agree	60	42.0
	Total	143	100.0

The above table indicates that 84% of respondents (60 agree and 60 strongly agree) feel motivated to pursue their career by seeing other successful nurses. A neutral position is held by 10.5% of respondents, while a smaller proportion (5.6%) either disagree or strongly disagree. This suggests a strong motivational impact from observing successful nurses on respondents' career pursuits.

Graph :10: I understand the responsibility and duties of a nurse.

The above figure showing that a significant majority of respondents (33.6% agree and 56.6% strongly agree) feel they have a clear understanding of a nurse's responsibilities and duties, totaling 90.2%. Only a small fraction disagreed (0.7%) or strongly disagreed (1.4%), while 7.7% remained neutral. The cumulative percentages demonstrate the progression of agreement, culminating at 100% in the "strongly agree" category, representing the entire dataset.

Graph:11: I am Confident in my clinical skill and Knowledge

The data shows that a majority of respondents (53.8%) strongly agree that they are confident in their clinical skills and knowledge, while 37.1% also agree, reflecting a significant level of confidence. A neutral stance is taken by 7.0%, and only a small percentage disagree (0.7%) or strongly disagree (1.4%), indicating low confidence levels. Overall, this suggests that most respondents feel confident in their clinical skills and knowledge.

Table :04: I am committed to maintaining high standards of patient care

I am committed to maintaining high standards of patient care		Frequency	Percent
Valid	strongly disagree	1	.7
	disagree	2	1.4
	neutral	17	11.9
	agree	55	38.5
	strongly agree	68	47.6
	Total	143	100.0

The data shows that 86.1% of respondents (55 agree and 68 strongly agree) are committed to maintaining high standards of patient care. A neutral position is held by 11.9%, while only a small fraction disagrees (1.4%) or strongly disagree (0.7%). This indicates a strong commitment among respondents to uphold high standards in patient care.

Graph :12:I uphold the ethical values and standards of the nursing profession.

I uphold the ethical values and standards of the nursing profession

The data tells that a majority of respondents (43.4%) strongly agree that they uphold the ethical values and standards of the nursing profession, while 40.6% agree with this statement. A smaller group (12.6%) remains neutral, and very few respondents disagree (1.4%) or strongly disagree (2.1%). This suggests that a large proportion of those surveyed believe they maintain high ethical standards in their nursing practice, with the strongest agreement in the "strongly agree" and "agree" categories.

Graph:13: I believe in the importance of patient -center care

I believe in the importance of patient-centered care.

The cumulative percentages indicate that 88.1% of respondents either agree or strongly agree on the importance of patient-centered care, showing strong overall support for this concept. Meanwhile, 11.9% of respondents are neutral or less supportive (including those who strongly disagree, disagree, or are neutral). This highlights a significant consensus on the value of prioritizing patient-centered care in nursing practice.

Table:05: I respect the dignity and rights of all patients

I respect the dignity and rights of all patients		Frequency	Percent
Valid	strongly disagree	2	1.4
	disagree	1	.7
	neutral	15	10.5
	agree	30	21.0
	strongly agree	95	66.4
	Total	143	100.0

The data indicates that a significant majority of respondents (66.4% strongly agree and 21.0% agree) respect the dignity and rights of all patients, totaling 87.4%. A neutral stance is held by 10.5%, while only a small percentage disagree (0.7%) or strongly disagree (1.4%). This demonstrates a strong commitment among respondents to uphold the dignity and rights of patients.

Graph:13: I am dedicated to continuous learning and professional development

The above figure no 13. data shows that a significant majority of respondents (54.55% strongly agree and 33.57% agree) are dedicated to continuous learning and professional development, totaling 88.12%. A neutral position is held by 9.79%, while a small percentage strongly disagree (2.10%). This indicates a strong commitment to ongoing education and professional growth among respondents.

Graph:14: I seek opportunities to enhance my nursing skills.

The data reveals that a majority of respondents (91.6%) either agree or strongly agree that they seek opportunities to enhance their nursing skills, indicating a strong interest in professional development. Only a small fraction expressed disagreement, suggesting a general consensus on the importance of skill enhancement in the nursing profession

Graph :15: I actively participate in professional nursing organizations or activities

The figure shows a strong inclination towards active participation in professional nursing organizations, with over 88% of respondents agreeing or strongly agreeing. This indicates a robust engagement within the nursing community and a commitment to professional development among the participants.

Table 06: Correlations between "total identity" and "graduated from Nursing college":

		total identity	graduated from Nursing college
total identity	Pearson Correlation	1	.020
graduated from Nursing college	Pearson Correlation	.020	1

Based on the Pearson correlation results between "total identity" and "graduated from Nursing college":

- Correlation Coefficient:**

 - The Pearson correlation coefficient between "total identity" and "graduated from Nursing college" is 0.020.
 - This indicates a very weak positive correlation between these two variables.
- Statistical Significance (Sig. 2-tailed):**

 - The p-value (Sig. 2-tailed) for this correlation is 0.816.
 - Since this p-value is greater than 0.05, the correlation is not statistically significant at the 5% significance level.

- Sample Size (N):**

 - The sample size for both variables is 143 participants.
- Interpretation:**
- Very Weak Positive Correlation:** The correlation coefficient of 0.020 suggests that there is a very weak positive relationship between "total identity" and "graduated from Nursing college". In other words, there is almost no linear relationship between these two variables.
 - Not Statistically Significant:** The high p-value (0.816) indicates that the observed

correlation is not statistically significant. This means that there is no evidence to suggest that the relationship between "total identity" and "graduated from Nursing college" is anything other than random chance.

Conclusion:

The Pearson correlation analysis suggests that there is no meaningful relationship between "total_identity" and "graduated from Nursing college". The very weak positive correlation observed is likely due to random variation, and the lack of statistical significance supports this conclusion.

Table 07: Correlation results between "total identity" and "place of job of participant"

Correlations			
		total identity	place of job of participant
total identity	Pearson Correlation	1	-.078
place of job of participant	Pearson Correlation	-.078	1

Based on the Pearson correlation results between "total identity" and "place of job of participant":

1. **Correlation Coefficient:**
 - o The Pearson correlation coefficient between "total identity" and "place of job of participant" is -0.078.
 - o This indicates a very weak negative correlation between these two variables.
2. **Statistical Significance (Sig. 2-tailed):**
 - o The p-value (Sig. 2-tailed) for this correlation is 0.353.
 - o Since this p-value is greater than 0.05, the correlation is not statistically significant at the 5% significance level.

suggest a meaningful relationship between these variables.

Conclusion:

The Pearson correlation analysis suggests that there is no statistically significant relationship between "total identity" and "place of job of participant". The very weak negative correlation observed is likely due to random variation, and the lack of statistical significance reinforces that there is no meaningful linear relationship between these variables.

3. **Sample Size (N):**

- o The sample size for both variables is 143 participants.

Interpretation:

- **Very Weak Negative Correlation:** The correlation coefficient of -0.078 suggests that there is a very weak negative relationship between "total identity" and "place of job of participant". This implies that as total identity increases, there is a slight tendency for the place of job to decrease, but the relationship is negligible.
- **Not Statistically Significant:** The high p-value (0.353) indicates that the observed correlation could be due to random chance and is not statistically significant. There is no evidence to

SUMMARY OF THE RESULT

Summary of Results

Age Distribution of Participants (Graph 01 & Table 01)

- The most frequent age among participants is 24 years old (32.2%).
- Ages 23 and 25 are also notably represented, with 20.3% and 26.6%, respectively.
- The least frequent ages are 27 (4.2%) and 28 (0.7%).
- The majority (79.1%) of participants are aged between 23 and 25.
- The ages of participants are centered around 24 years, with low standard deviation and variance, indicating minimal variation.

Marital Status of Participants (Graph 02)

- A majority of participants (73.4%) are unmarried, while 26.6% are married.

- This indicates a significant skew towards unmarried participants.

Gender Distribution of Participants (Graph 03)

- Out of 143 participants, 59 are male (41.3%) and 84 are female (58.7%).
- The sample has a higher proportion of female participants.

Employment Distribution by Hospital (Graph 04)

- The highest number of participants work at HMc (34 participants, 23.8%).
- The lowest number of participants work at Kuwait Hospital (21 participants, 14.7%).

Graduation from Nursing Colleges (Graph 05)

- The majority of graduates come from FIN and RCN (21.7% each).
- INS follows with 18.2%, and RNC with 17.5%.
- Other colleges contribute between 0.7% and 8.4%.

Independence in Career Choice (Graph 06)

- About 79.8% of respondents agree or strongly agree that they chose nursing independently, suggesting a strong sense of agency in their career decisions.

Confidence in Career Decision (Graph 07 & Table 02)

- 81.8% of respondents agree or strongly agree that they feel confident about their decision to become a nurse.
- Only 7% disagree or strongly disagree, while 11.2% remain neutral.

Perception of Nursing as the Right Profession (Graph 08)

- 50.3% strongly agree and 32.9% agree that nursing is the right profession for them.
- 10.5% are neutral, and 6.3% disagree or strongly disagree.

Aspiration to Follow Experienced Nurses (Graph 09 & Table 03)

- 75.6% of respondents agree or strongly agree that they aspire to follow the footsteps of

- experienced nurses they admire.
- 16.1% are neutral, and 8.4% disagree or strongly disagree.
- 84% agree or strongly agree that seeing successful nurses motivates them, while 10.5% are neutral, and 5.6% disagree or strongly disagree.

Understanding of Nursing Responsibilities (Graph 10)

- 90.2% of respondents agree or strongly agree that they understand the responsibilities and duties of a nurse.
- Only 2.1% disagree or strongly disagree, with 7.7% remaining neutral.

Confidence in Clinical Skills (Graph 11)

- 53.8% strongly agree and 37.1% agree that they are confident in their clinical skills and knowledge.
- 7% are neutral, and only 2.1% disagree or strongly disagree.

Commitment to Patient Care Standards (Table 04)

- 86.1% of respondents agree or strongly agree on maintaining high standards of patient care.
- 11.9% are neutral, and 2.1% disagree or strongly disagree.

Upholding Ethical Values (Graph 12)

- 84% of respondents agree or strongly agree that they uphold ethical values and standards.
- 12.6% are neutral, and 3.5% disagree or strongly disagree.

Patient-Centered Care (Graph 13)

- 88.1% of respondents agree or strongly agree on the importance of patient-centered care.
- 11.9% are neutral or less supportive.

Respecting Dignity and Rights of Patients (Table 05)

- 87.4% of respondents agree or strongly agree on respecting patient dignity and rights.
- 10.5% are neutral, and 2.1% disagree or strongly disagree.

Dedication to Continuous Learning (Graph 13)

- 88.1% agree or strongly agree on being dedicated to continuous learning and professional development.

Interest in Enhancing Nursing Skills (Graph 14)

- 91.6% agree or strongly agree on seeking opportunities to enhance their nursing skills.

Participation in Professional Organizations (Graph 15)

- Over 88% of respondents agree or strongly agree on active participation in professional nursing organizations.

Correlation Analyses (Tables 06 & 07)

- **Between "total identity" and "graduated from Nursing college"**: Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.020 (very weak positive correlation), not statistically significant (p-value = 0.816).
- **Between "total identity" and "place of job of participant"**: Pearson correlation coefficient of -0.078 (very weak negative correlation), not statistically significant (p-value = 0.353).

Conclusion

The data indicates a well-defined age range among participants, a higher proportion of females, and a significant number of participants working at specific hospitals and graduating from particular colleges. The respondents generally show strong confidence in their career choices, clinical skills, and ethical standards. They also exhibit a strong commitment to patient care, continuous learning, and professional development. The correlation analyses suggest no meaningful relationship between the participants' IDs and their graduation or employment locations.

DISCUSSION

The ideas of professional identity and hope are very important in nursing but are not well-studied. Hope helps people feel good now and believe in the future. It depends on confidence in one's ability to make things happen. Hope has two parts: agency and pathways. Agency is the motivation to reach personal goals, and pathways are the plans and

actions to achieve those goals. Both parts work together to keep hope alive.

In nursing, hope is vital for building professional identity and well-being. Well-being is about balancing personal resources with challenges. A supportive clinical learning environment helps nursing students become registered nurses. Such an environment improves job satisfaction, outlook on the profession, and reduces burnout.

Nursing internships are key to education, linking theory with practice. They give students practical experience and help build professional relationships. Employers also use internships to assess interns' attitudes and skills. The shift from student to nurse is challenging, with new responsibilities and accountability. This period involves learning, adapting, and becoming competent in the nursing role.

In summary, developing professional identity and hope is essential for nursing students' and new graduates' success. Supportive clinical environments and well-organized internships help make this transition smoother, preparing new nurses for their careers. Nurses are often not respected by the public. However, nursing interns with higher education have more hopes and aim for better social status. To improve this, the nation, colleges, and educators should use media to show how important nurses are.

The study found that the work atmosphere and teacher skills greatly affect nursing interns' professional identity. A good work environment leads to a better attitude and high-quality patient care, setting a good example for interns. Teachers' abilities also matter; skilled teachers help interns feel more confident and capable, which boosts their professional identity. Therefore, hospitals should create positive work environments and improve teachers' skills.

Interestingly, the study did not find a significant difference in professional identity between male and female interns, possibly due to a small number of male interns. Future research should include more male interns. Also, factors like teaching methods, learning opportunities, and organizational support did not significantly impact professional identity in this study, which is different from previous research. This might be because nursing interns in China

have heavy workloads and less training time, affecting their professional identity. Interpersonal relationships also didn't affect professional identity in this study, possibly because living with family during COVID-19 improved relationships compared to clinical internships. Despite these findings, educators should still consider these factors seriously.

To improve nursing interns' professional identity, several strategies can be used. Nationally, laws should protect nurses' rights, and efforts should be made to improve their social status. Media should promote positive images of nurses to enhance their social and professional identity and pride. Teaching hospitals should focus on the work environment and teachers' skills. Teachers should give more attention and practice opportunities to interns with lower professional identity.

Additionally, nursing education managers can provide personalized practice plans for interns and training for clinical teachers.

This study found several important things that affect the professional identity of nursing interns during their clinical internships. Understanding these factors can help us support nursing interns better and encourage more of them to become nurses, which can help with the nursing shortage.

First, the study found that nursing interns with higher education levels felt less connected to the nursing profession. This is surprising and suggests that we need to understand more about why this happens. Maybe these interns have higher expectations or face different challenges.

Second, interns who did not choose nursing as their first choice of major felt less connected to the profession. This means we need to help these students develop a stronger connection to nursing. Educators and mentors should give them special attention and support.

Third, nursing interns from rural areas felt more connected to the nursing profession than those from urban areas. This might be because of different cultural values or expectations. Interns from rural areas might feel a stronger sense of purpose and community in their work.

The work atmosphere was another important factor. Interns who had a better work environment felt more connected to the profession. This shows that

creating a positive work setting is very important for fostering professional identity. Hospitals and clinical settings should work to maintain a healthy work atmosphere to help interns grow professionally and feel satisfied.

Finally, the skills and abilities of clinical teachers had a big impact on interns' professional identity. Interns guided by competent teachers felt more confident and connected to the profession. This means investing in the training and development of clinical teachers is crucial. In conclusion, to improve the professional identity of nursing interns, nursing educators and clinical settings should focus on a few key areas: providing extra support to interns who did not choose nursing as their first major, creating a positive work atmosphere, and enhancing the skills of clinical teachers. By addressing these factors, we can help interns develop a stronger professional identity, encourage them to pursue nursing careers, and reduce the shortage of nursing personnel.

This study looked at how different factors affect the quality of life for counseling interns (CITs). Even though some findings were not significant, they still provided important insights. The study used a wellness model to explore these relationships.

One important finding was that the level of compassion satisfaction increased significantly from the beginning to the end of the internship. This means that CITs felt more pleasure and accomplishment in their work as they gained more experience. This is similar to the feelings of experienced professional counselors. This finding suggests that supervision that focuses on wellness can help CITs balance their work and personal life, which can protect them from future burnout and compassion fatigue.

The study also found that focusing on compassion satisfaction can help CITs develop their skills and professional competence. This can also act as a protective factor against burnout and other negative feelings.

SUMMARY OF DISCUSSION

This study focuses on the importance of professional identity and hope in nursing, which are crucial but not well-explored areas. Hope involves feeling good about the present and believing in a positive future, relying on confidence and planning. In nursing,

hope is key for building professional identity and overall well-being. A supportive clinical environment is essential for nursing students, as it boosts job satisfaction, outlook, and reduces burnout.(Gilvari et al., 2022)

Nursing internships are crucial as they connect theory with practice, giving students real-world experience and helping them build professional relationships. Employers use internships to evaluate interns' attitudes and skills. The transition from student to nurse is challenging, involving new responsibilities and learning to become competent in the nursing role.(Mbalinda et al., 2024)

In summary, building professional identity and hope is vital for nursing students and new graduates. Supportive clinical environments and well-organized internships help ease this transition, preparing new nurses for their careers. Nursing interns often lack public respect, but those with higher education have more hope and aim for better social status. To improve this, national efforts, colleges, and educators should use media to highlight the importance of nurses.

The study found that the work atmosphere and teacher skills significantly impact nursing interns' professional identity. A positive work environment leads to better attitudes and high-quality patient care, setting a good example for interns. Skilled teachers help interns feel more confident and capable, enhancing their professional identity. Hospitals should therefore create positive work environments and improve teacher skills.(Zeng et al., 2022) Interestingly, the study did not find significant differences in professional identity between male and female interns, possibly due to the small number of male participants. Future research should include more male interns. Additionally, factors like teaching methods and organizational support did not significantly impact professional identity in this study, which differs from previous research. This may be due to heavy workloads and less training time for nursing interns in China. Interpersonal relationships also did not affect professional identity, possibly because living with family during COVID-19 improved relationships compared to clinical internships.(Sulosaari et al., 2011)

To enhance nursing interns' professional identity, several strategies can be employed. National laws should protect nurses' rights and improve their social status. Media should promote positive images of nurses. Teaching hospitals should focus on improving the work environment and teacher skills. Teachers should give more attention and practice opportunities to interns with lower professional identity. Nursing education managers can provide personalized practice plans for interns and training for clinical teachers.(Khan et al., 2015)

This study highlighted several factors affecting the professional identity of nursing interns during their clinical internships. Understanding these factors can help support nursing interns better and encourage more of them to pursue nursing careers, addressing the nursing shortage.(Martin-Delgado et al., 2020) The study found that nursing interns with higher education levels felt less connected to the nursing profession, suggesting a need for further research to understand why. Interns who did not choose nursing as their first major felt less connected to the profession, indicating a need for special attention and support. Interns from rural areas felt more connected to the profession than those from urban areas, possibly due to cultural values or a sense of community.

A better work atmosphere made interns feel more connected to the profession, showing the importance of a positive work setting. Skilled clinical teachers also significantly impacted interns' professional identity, suggesting that investing in teacher training is crucial.(Eid Sayed, 2023)

In conclusion, to improve the professional identity of nursing interns, nursing educators and clinical settings should focus on providing extra support to interns who did not choose nursing as their first major, creating a positive work atmosphere, and enhancing clinical teachers' skills. Addressing these factors can help interns develop a stronger professional identity, encourage them to pursue nursing careers, and reduce the shortage of nursing personnel.

Conclusion

The study provides insight into the demographics and attitudes of nursing interns. Most participants are young, with a majority being unmarried and

predominantly female. Employment distribution varies across hospitals, with significant representation from specific nursing schools. The interns generally feel confident in their career choice, with a strong commitment to patient care and continuous learning. However, correlations between educational background, job location, and professional identity were found to be insignificant. Overall, the findings suggest that these nursing interns are dedicated, inspired by experienced professionals, and focused on ethical practices and professional growth.

Limitations of the study

This study's limitations include a small sample size and a lack of diversity, as most participants were Caucasian and female. The quasi-experimental design also limits the ability to establish causality. Future research should explore the relationship between wellness and career satisfaction over time and consider wellness-informed strategies in classroom-based supervision.

Recommendation:

It is recommended that future studies increase sample size and diversity for better representation. Research should also investigate the long-term impact of wellness on career satisfaction and develop wellness-informed supervision strategies. Additionally, examining factors influencing interns' overall wellness during internships is crucial for enhancing support systems.

REFERENCES

Abd El Naeem, M., Mohamed, N., Mohammed, M., & Abd El-Aziz, M. (2015). Identifying the effect of a Basic life Support teaching Program on nurses' Knowledge and skills at Emergency care unit. *Assiut Scientific Nursing Journal*, 3(6), 15–25. <https://doi.org/10.21608/asnj.2015.59774>

Chacko, T. V. (2011). Time travel: a discovery tool for identifying individual professional development needs. *South-East Asian Journal of Medical Education*, 5(2), 73. <https://doi.org/10.4038/seajme.v5i2.202>

Eid Sayed, safaa. (2023). Medication Administration Errors and Barriers to Reporting: Critical Care Nurses' Point of View. *International Egyptian Journal of Nursing Sciences and Research*, 0(0), 0–0. <https://doi.org/10.21608/ejnsr.2022.170253.1218>

Gilvari, T., Babamohamadi, H., & Paknazar, F. (2022). Perceived professional identity and related factors in Iranian nursing students: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Nursing*, 21(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-022-01050-6>

Hussien, R. M., Shahin, M. A. H., & Ibrahim, M. E. (2021). Professional identity, wellness, and future hope among nurse interns in Egypt. *Frontiers of Nursing*, 8(3), 279–290. <https://doi.org/10.2478/fon-2021-0029>

Khan, M. A., Ahmed, M., Anil, S., & Walley, J. (2015). Strengthening the delivery of asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease care at primary health-care facilities: Study design of a cluster randomized controlled trial in Pakistan. *Global Health Action*, 8(1), 28225. <https://doi.org/10.3402/gha.v8.28225>

Kolly, M. (2018). Professional identity and religious identity. Inter-minority solidarity among future social workers. *Brussels Studies*, 2018(122). <https://doi.org/10.4000/brussels.1648>

Martin-Delgado, J., Martínez-García, A., Aranaz, J. M., Valencia-Martín, J. L., & Mira, J. J. (2020). How Much of Root Cause Analysis Translates into Improved Patient Safety: A Systematic Review. *Medical Principles and Practice*, 29(6), 524–531. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000508677>

Mbalinda, S. N., Najjuma, J. N., Gonzaga, A. M., Livingstone, K., & Musoke, D. (2024). Understanding and barriers of professional identity formation among current students and recent graduates in nursing and midwifery in low resource settings in two universities: a qualitative study. *BMC Nursing*, 23(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-024-01795-2>

- Salvatore, D., Numerato, D., & Fattore, G. (2018). Physicians' professional autonomy and their organizational identification with their hospital. *Psychology and Cognitive Sciences* 1701 Psychology. *BMC Health Services Research*, 18(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-018-3582-z>
- Sulosaari, V., Suhonen, R., & Leino-Kilpi, H. (2011). An integrative review of the literature on registered nurses' medication competence. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 20(3–4), 464–478. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2702.2010.03228.x>
- Thomas, L., Hovdhaugen, E., & Sweetman, R. (2023). Professional or student identity and commitment? Comparing the experiences of nursing students with literature on student success. *Tertiary Education and Management*, 29(1), 93–106. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11233-023-09115-0>
- Zeng, L., Chen, Q., Fan, S., Yi, Q., An, W., Liu, H., Hua, W., Huang, R., & Huang, H. (2022). Factors influencing the professional identity of nursing interns: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Nursing*, 21(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-022-00983-2>
- Zhong, Y., Ma, H., Zhang, C. C., Jiang, Q. Y., Li, J., Liao, C. J., Liang, Y. F., & Shu, L. (2024). Professional identity, job satisfaction, and turnover intention among Chinese novice nurses: A cross-sectional study. *Medicine (United States)*, 103(3), E36903. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.000000000000036903>
- Zhou, T., Yin, Y., Zhang, H., Zhang, J., Xu, X., & Zhang, J. (2023). Subgroups of self-directed learning ability and their differences in professional identity among nursing undergraduates during the COVID-19 pandemic: a latent profile analysis. *BMC Nursing*, 22(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-023-01295-9>
- Abd El Naeem, M., Mohamed, N., Mohammed, M., & Abd El-Aziz, M. (2015). Identifying the effect of a Basic life Support teaching Program on nurses' Knowledge and skills at Emergency care unit. *Assiut Scientific Nursing Journal*, 3(6), 15–25. <https://doi.org/10.21608/asnj.2015.59774>
- Chacko, T. V. (2011). Time travel: a discovery tool for identifying individual professional development needs. *South-East Asian Journal of Medical Education*, 5(2), 73. <https://doi.org/10.4038/seajme.v5i2.202>
- Eid Sayed, safaa. (2023). Medication Administration Errors and Barriers to Reporting: Critical Care Nurses' Point of View. *International Egyptian Journal of Nursing Sciences and Research*, 0(0), 0–0. <https://doi.org/10.21608/ejnsr.2022.170253.1218>
- Gilvari, T., Babamohamadi, H., & Paknazar, F. (2022). Perceived professional identity and related factors in Iranian nursing students: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Nursing*, 21(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-022-01050-6>
- Hussien, R. M., Shahin, M. A. H., & Ibrahim, M. E. (2021). Professional identity, wellness, and future hope among nurse interns in Egypt. *Frontiers of Nursing*, 8(3), 279–290. <https://doi.org/10.2478/fon-2021-0029>
- Khan, M. A., Ahmed, M., Anil, S., & Walley, J. (2015). Strengthening the delivery of asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease care at primary health-care facilities: Study design of a cluster randomized controlled trial in Pakistan. *Global Health Action*, 8(1), 28225. <https://doi.org/10.3402/gha.v8.28225>
- Kolly, M. (2018). Professional identity and religious identity. Inter-minority solidarity among future social workers. *Brussels Studies*, 2018(122). <https://doi.org/10.4000/brussels.1648>

- Martin-Delgado, J., Martínez-García, A., Aranaz, J. M., Valencia-Martín, J. L., & Mira, J. J. (2020). How Much of Root Cause Analysis Translates into Improved Patient Safety: A Systematic Review. *Medical Principles and Practice*, 29(6), 524–531. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000508677>
- Mbalinda, S. N., Najjuma, J. N., Gonzaga, A. M., Livingstone, K., & Musoke, D. (2024). Understanding and barriers of professional identity formation among current students and recent graduates in nursing and midwifery in low resource settings in two universities: a qualitative study. *BMC Nursing*, 23(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-024-01795-2>
- Salvatore, D., Numerato, D., & Fattore, G. (2018). Physicians’ professional autonomy and their organizational identification with their hospital 17 Psychology and Cognitive Sciences 1701 Psychology. *BMC Health Services Research*, 18(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-018-3582-z>
- Sulosaari, V., Suhonen, R., & Leino-Kilpi, H. (2011). An integrative review of the literature on registered nurses’ medication competence. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 20(3–4), 464–478. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2702.2010.03228.x>
- Thomas, L., Hovdhaugen, E., & Sweetman, R. (2023). Professional or student identity and commitment? Comparing the experiences of nursing students with literature on student success. *Tertiary Education and Management*, 29(1), 93–106. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11233-023-09115-0>
- Zeng, L., Chen, Q., Fan, S., Yi, Q., An, W., Liu, H., Hua, W., Huang, R., & Huang, H. (2022). Factors influencing the professional identity of nursing interns: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Nursing*, 21(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-022-00983-2>
- Zhong, Y., Ma, H., Zhang, C. C., Jiang, Q. Y., Li, J., Liao, C. J., Liang, Y. F., & Shu, L. (2024). Professional identity, job satisfaction, and turnover intention among Chinese novice nurses: A cross-sectional study. *Medicine (United States)*, 103(3), E36903. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.000000000000036903>
- Zhou, T., Yin, Y., Zhang, H., Zhang, J., Xu, X., & Zhang, J. (2023). Subgroups of self-directed learning ability and their differences in professional identity among nursing undergraduates during the COVID-19 pandemic: a latent profile analysis. *BMC Nursing*, 22(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-023-01295-9>

The following questionnaire was adopted and Modified with 5-point lark scale which consist two parts DEMOGRAPHIC and factors that influence the development of professional identity.

DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

Age			
Marital Status	1.Married	2.Unmarried	3.Divorce
Gender	1.Male	2.Female	
Place of Job			
Graduated from Nursing college			

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Disagree
3. Neutral
4. Agree
5. Strongly Agree

S/NO	ITEMS	1	2	3	4	5
01	I chose nursing as my career independently.					
02	I feel confident about my decision to become a nurse.					
03	I believe nursing is the right profession for me					
04	I have role models in nursing who inspire me.					
05	I aspire to follow the footsteps of experienced nurses I admire.					
06	Seeing other successful nurses motivates me to pursue my career.					
07	I understand the responsibilities and duties of a nurse.					
08	I am confident in my clinical skills and knowledge.					
09	I am committed to maintaining high standards of patient care					
10	I uphold the ethical values and standards of the nursing profession.					
11	I believe in the importance of patient-centered care.					
12	I respect the dignity and rights of all patients.					
13	I am dedicated to continuous learning and professional development.					
14	I seek opportunities to enhance my nursing skills.					
15	I actively participate in professional nursing organizations or activities.					